

How do historians study the uprisings of 1911 in Champagne? State of Literature.

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Abstract

Today, it is rare to find remnants of the subversive events which unfolded in 1911 in the two French departments of the Marne and the Aube in the Champagne wine region (situated in the northeast of France, 130 km from Paris). The year 1911 in Champagne is usually described as a “revolution,” a “revolt,” a “riot” or even a “crisis.” However, it is also considered as a founding event of the notion of the “modern vineyard.” According to the current narratives of local territorial actors (winegrowers, politicians, professionals in the tourism, wine market and heritage sector), the events played an important role in the delimitation of the Champagne wine region in 1927. It is also considered that the events contributed to the establishment of the Interprofessional Comity of the Champagne wine in 1941 which represents the interests of winegrowers and trade houses.

Indeed, tension was at the edge of eruption among winegrowers in the Marne and the Aube. Despite the fact that the demonstrations had different objectives in the two departments, numerous shared reasons caused their discontent: the devastation caused by the phylloxera, fraud of the wine market, the delimitation process of the wine region, poverty among winegrowers and the growing emphasis for white sparkling wine at the expense of the traditional red wine. When studying these events, historians have largely analysed these social and economic factors, as well as the role played by winegrowers in the events.

The objective of this paper is, first, to outline the main features and phases of the delimitation process of the wine region from 1903 to 1927, which appeared in the media in 1911 as a synonym of a “20 years of war” period and which has contributed to the events unfolding in 1911. Second, the article will analyse the various interpretations of the events of 1911 proposed by scholars and amateur historians since 1930. The aim would be here to draw the contours of the Francophone historiography of these events. The article concludes by reconsidering the different meanings of the notions of revolution, revolt, riot and crisis, through the lens of this historiography.

Introduction

One of the particularities of the nomination file of the Champagne Hillsides, Houses and Cellars UNESCO World Heritage site is its focus on the historical events occurring from the end of the nineteenth century up to the middle of the twentieth century. The narrative constructed in the nomination file puts a strong emphasis on the circumstances which lead to the establishment of an inter-professional organization between winegrowers and trade houses in 1941. Progressively, the model of this organization has multiplied, leading to a complex system of organizations, setting out a model that is adopted today worldwide.¹ One of the main factors that led to the creation of an organization system was the multiple tensions between winegrowers and trade houses especially which concerned the delimitation of the Champagne wine region. The delimitation aims to control the wine market and to protect the *appellation* against usurpation as well as to differentiate the products of the Champagne wine region from

¹ Haut Conseil de la Coopération Agricole, La filière viticole Française, (2017): 14.

other concurrent wines. The delimitation process lasted nearly 25 years, from 1903 to 1927. It was characterized by harsh debates from which a central state controversy emerged and became subject of national policy. The revolt of the winegrowers in the departments of the Marne and of the Aube in 1911 was a turning point.

Many researchers in social sciences focused on the events of 1911. Described by some as a riot, or as a revolution by others, it is also considered as a founding event of the notion of the “modern vineyard.”² A hundred years after, a local journal remembered the events of 1911 as the “revolt which laid the foundations for the most famous wine in the world”.³ However, before accepting any denomination proposed by scholars, it seems important to look at France’s political context in which the events took place. In 1905 the National Assembly approved the law on the separation of Church and State, and the French Section of the Workers' International was founded. As for the question of social unrest in the sector, protests emerged by wine growers in the Languedoc area situated in the south of France in 1907. The harsh rebellion caused the death of multiple victims, rapidly reaching regional scale, but was finally repressed by the government of Georges Clemenceau.⁴ Consequently, the media and the politicians asked questions about the rioters in Champagne. Who initiated the revolt? Was there any political idea behind the events? Was there any foreign interference aiming to manipulate the rioters? When looking at these questions, one should not forget that at the end of the French “*Belle époque*,” there were many political tensions in the French society and the enemies could have been foreigners (Germans, English, Russians), as well as fellow citizens (Socialists, Anarchists).

² Aline Brochot, “Analyse comparative des processus de construction sociale et territoriale du patrimoine dans les vignobles de Champagne et de Tokaj”, (Paris, Ministère de la Culture et de la francophonie, 1997), 109.

³ Stéphane Guerrini, “Il y a un siècle... Révoltés, les vigneron s'unissaient”, *L'Union*, (2011).

⁴ Jean Sagnes, “Le mouvement de 1907 en Languedoc-Roussillon: de la révolte viticole à la révolte régionale”, *Le Mouvement social* 104 (1978): 3.

In the first part of this article, I will describe the social and economic context of the Champagne region from 1890, in order to understand the circumstances in which the events took place in 1911. In the second part, we will discuss the delimitation process of the wine region which pays particular attention to the triggering factors of the events. Finally, in the third part, we will study how historians addressed the events of 1911 through the analysis of the relevant historiographical literature. Without trying to answer the question of whether the events in 1911 constituted a revolution, a revolt or a riot, I seek to explore why and when these events were perceived as such.

The social and economic context of the Champagne wine region from 1890 to 1911

The white sparkling wine market in Champagne was very successful in production during the second part of the nineteenth century. In 1780 more than 350.000 bottles were sold, in 1830 more than 3 million bottles, and between 1895 and 1910 the number of bottles sold reached 40 million.⁵ While white sparkling wine was traditionally produced in the abbeys and the homes of bourgeois landowners in Epernay between 1720–1730, and in Reims between 1760–1770, traders from mainly the textile industry and banking sector invested in the production and the selling of white sparkling wine at the turn of the 18th century.⁶ The industrial revolution also facilitated its development (development of transport, urbanization, progressive control of the oenological process, modernization of cellars). The production of white sparkling wine became an industrial process and the trade houses became fully-fledged industrial establishments. The mass production of champagne also required many infrastructures which were singularly visible

⁵ UNESCO nomination file of the site “Hillsides, Houses and Cellars“, Association Paysages du Champagne, (2014), 170.

⁶ UNESCO nomination file of the site “Hillsides, Houses and Cellars“, Association Paysages du Champagne, (2014), 159.

in the architecture of the trade houses and in the urban development of the towns like Reims, Épernay, Châlons-en-Champagne or Aÿ where the most trade houses were set up. It created an agro-industrial system that has profoundly marked the spatial and social organization of the Champagne region.⁷

As nearly a quarter-century passed, the wine began to deteriorate in the Gard area (situated in the south of France) because of the arrival of the phylloxera. It reached the department of the Aube in 1887.⁸ But, despite the deplorable harvest quantity, the region doubled its selling on the wine market. The trade houses purchased grapes and wine from other wine regions outside of Champagne (Anjou, Touraine, Metz etc). In consequence, it dropped the price of the grapes. The economic situation of the winegrowers worsened. This phenomenon was also remarkable in the statistics of the surface area of the vineyard. When 62.000 ha of wine area were registered in 1840, the surface area was only 49.000 ha fifty years later.⁹ The damages of the phylloxera (high expenses, uprooting vines, loss of harvest, abandonment of the work of wine growing) caused important economic and social difficulties in the region. Many winegrowers lost their revenues and impoverished. Their income depended mainly on the purchase volume of the trade houses. Besides, as mentioned before, the Champagne wine region was mainly a red wine-producing region until the end of the nineteenth century, when the production of sparkling white wine became dominant. Though, the production of white sparkling wine was more expensive for winegrowers. Thus, the overall dependence of winegrowers on the trade houses increased. Market fraud and the devastating consequences of phylloxera further increased the demand to

⁷ UNESCO nomination file of the site “Hillsides, Houses and Cellars“, Association Paysages du Champagne (2014), 173.

⁸ Claudine Wolikow and Serge Wolikow, Champagne ! Histoire inattendue (Paris: Les éditions de l’Atelier), 112

⁹ UNESCO nomination file of the site “Hillsides, Houses and Cellars“, Association Paysages du Champagne (2014), 175.

establish strict regulation on wine trading, with the aim of protecting the origin of the grape variety and the production of wine with a geographical delimitation.

The delimitation process of the Champagne wine region

The Champagne wine region is situated in the northeast of France and it stretches over five departments, covering 34.000 ha: Aisne, Aube, Marne, Seine-et-Marne, Haut-Marne. The Marne and the Aube departments are the most densely covered by vineyards. This production area was defined in 1927 by the result of a delimitation process which was analysed by historians such as Claudine Wolikow and Claire Desbois-Thibault. I present the delimitation process on the basis of their research. According to them, the process can be described in three stages.¹⁰ First, the preliminary work carried out by the General Council (departmental level) of the Marne from 1903 to 1914. Second, the circumstances of the adoption of the law on the appellation (designation) in 1919 will be. And third, the finalization of the delimitation process of the Champagne wine region in 1927.

The delimitation process in the Champagne wine region was launched in 1903 by the General Council of the Marne's Department and the Champagne Wine Trade Union, created in 1882 on the initiative of the champagne trade houses like Heidsieck, Mumm and Moët. Their main objective was to protect the market of the sparkling wine which was processed in the Champagne region by forbidding the use of the name of champagne for other wine regions. The members of the Union proposed to geographically delimitate the wine region. The demand emerged from the local level, but it was actually a part of a national process that was started

¹⁰ Claire Desbois-Thibault, "La délimitation de la Champagne viticole: un processus lent et tumultueux", June 17, 2016, in *Inauguration de l'Institut Georges Chappaz de la Vigne et du Vin en Champagne* conference, video, 28: 53, <https://mediacenter.univ-reims.fr/channels/GeorgesCHAPPAZ/media/MEDIA161003084738991>.

with the approval by the National Assembly of the so-called Chaptal Act on 28 July 1894, named after the rapporteur of the text.¹¹ This law enforced the protection of the commercial name and the geographical origin of the products against alterations of names, within the framework of the protection of commercial property. Since 1820, sparkling wines were produced in Metz, Toul, Arbois under the name of champagne. Mainly trade houses initiated legal procedures against this kind of usurpation. Concerning the denomination of the Champagne region, the first restrictions were established in 1887: from this date, only the sparkling wine which was harvested and produced in Champagne was eligible to the name of “champagne” or “vin de champagne” on the bottles. The State High Court required that the perimeter of the geographical delimitation area correspond to the borders of the government of Champagne and Brie which was an administrative area of the Ancien Régime (1589-1789).¹²

Furthermore, an act repressing fraud was approved in 1905. This law allowed to begin the work on the delimitation of the area by the Council of the Marne and the Champagne Wine Trade Union. Thus, in November 1905, a first reunion was organized at the Ministry of Agriculture, with the participation of the Union and the Federation of the unions of winegrowers from the Marne, created in 1904. The members of this Federation were local anti-fraud unions which became later the Champagne growers union in 1919, setting out as a principal objective the total repression of fraud.

The delimitation proposed to cover the department of the Marne and a part of Condé-en-Brie's region. The proposition was forwarded to the State Council in June 1907, provoking the first manifestations in the department of the Aube against the proposition.¹³ The manifestations

¹¹ Claudine Wolikow, “La délimitation de la Champagne“ in *Les Cahiers de la Villa Bissinger* (Institut International des vins de Champagne, 2010), 142.

¹² Claudine Wolikow, “La délimitation de la Champagne“ in *Les Cahiers de la Villa Bissinger* (Institut International des vins de Champagne, 2010), 146.

¹³ Claudine Wolikow, “La délimitation de la Champagne“ in *Les Cahiers de la Villa Bissinger* (Institut International des vins de Champagne, 2010), 147.

notwithstanding, the State Council published a decree on the 17th of December 1908. The decree covered a delimitation of an area of 15.631 ha which involved the Marne department, 44 villages of the district of Château Thierry, and 36 villages of the district of Soissons.¹⁴ Aube's department was beyond the decree's scope as the image below illustrates. In this context, winegrowers in the Marne department chose to ask additional regulation to repress fraud, but in the Aube, demonstrations were growing rapidly as being excluded from the Champagne

production area and by then forbidding to produce wine under the designation of Champagne.

Image 1: Delimitation area according to the decree published on the 17th of December

¹⁴ Claudine Wolikow, “La délimitation de la Champagne“ in *Les Cahiers de la Villa Bissinger* (Institut International des vins de Champagne, 2010), 146.

(Source: Claude Wolikow <https://preo.u-bourgogne.fr/territoiresduvin/index.php?id=1444>)
modified by Krisztina Albert

Indeed, a series of demonstrations took place in October 1909 in the Marne demanding additional regulation from the authorities. On the 16th of October 1910, 10.000 demonstrators gathered in Epernay. More than two months of tax resistance actions were launched. At the same time, the department of the Aube was claiming the right to be part of the Champagne wine region. On the 19th of March 1910, further demonstrations were organized in Bar-sur-Aube, regrouping more than 5.000 persons.¹⁵ Gaston Cheq, deputy mayor in the municipality of Bar-sur-Aube was one of the leaders of the manifestations in the Aube. He created the Federation of wine growers of the Aube by the establishment of central committees in Bar-sur-Aube and Bar-sur-Seine, two central towns in the Aube. However, a difference can be discerned in the composition of these committees: in Bar-sur-Aube wine growers were in minority compared to notabilities, unlike in Bar-sur-Seine the central committee was dominantly composed of wine growers compared to elected notabilities, mayors, town councils etc.¹⁶

Finally, on the 10th of February 1911, additional measures were voted by the Senate. However, these measures blocked the winegrowers who were situated in the Aube, by providing grapes or wine to the trade houses situated in the Marne. This measure was judged unfair because winegrowers from the Aube were providing wine to trade houses in the Marne since 1849.¹⁷

Afterwards, a decision increased the manifestations in the Marne: the Senate deleted the decree on the administrative delimitation on 11th of April 1911. This decision made the Marne's wine growers furious. Indeed, the winegrowers of the Marne relaunched the demonstrations because due to this decision all measures gained during their work on the delimitation since 1903 were

¹⁵ Claudine Wolikow and Serge Wolikow, *Champagne ! Histoire inattendue* (Paris: Les éditions de l'Atelier), 112

¹⁶ Fabrice Perron and Yann Harlaut, *Les révoltes du champagne*, (Editions Dominique Guéniot, 2011), 53.

¹⁷ Fabrice Perron, "L'approvisionnement aubois des maisons de champagne marnaises avant 1911", *Annales de la Société Historique de Bar-sur-Aube et du pays baralbin* 1 (2018): 17.

being deleted. We can observe here how the demonstrators responded separately to the different decisions made by the Senate. Demonstrators were considered by the media as revolutionaries.¹⁸ Wine growers refused to pay taxes, and the elected representatives resigned.¹⁹ Finally, the agitations were repressed by 15.000 soldiers.²⁰ The arguments coming from the Marne against the inclusion of the Aube was referring to the issue of overproduction which could have lower prices and could have led to poor sales.²¹

Similarly, in Aube, the abolition of the decree did not calm the situation and demonstrations increased. On the 7th of June 1911, a new ministerial decree was adopted, in which the Aube department was qualified as a “second zone of Champagne”. Due to this qualification, the winegrowers of the Aube felt humiliated. On the 30th of June of 1911, the Minister of Agriculture called Jules Pams proposed a new project of law that completed the law of Chaptal by creating a protection of the *appellations d’origine* (designation of origin).²² In 1913, the process to adapt the law was interrupted because of the start of the First World War. The project was reconsidered in February 1919 and was finally adopted in May 1919. From this time, the declaration of the harvest and stock was an obligation.²³ In 1925, 6 villages in Aube acquired the appellation. In 1927, the delimitation of the Champagne wine region was reviewed, and a new delimitation area was decided with the inclusion of the villages of Aube: 272 villages of the Marne, 71 from the Aube, 51 in the department of the Aisne, 5 in the Seine-et-Marne and 2 in the Haute-Marne.²⁴

¹⁸ Gérard Munier, “La révolte marnaise 1911”, *Folklore de Champagne*, 78 (April 1982): 10

¹⁹ Claudine Wolikow and Serge Wolikow, *Champagne ! Histoire inattendue* (Paris: Les éditions de l’Atelier), 148

²⁰ Claudine Wolikow and Serge Wolikow, *Champagne ! Histoire inattendue* (Paris: Les éditions de l’Atelier), 148

²¹ Claudine Wolikow and Serge Wolikow, *Champagne ! Histoire inattendue* (Paris: Les éditions de l’Atelier), 140

²² Claudine Wolikow, “La délimitation de la Champagne“ in *Les Cahiers de la Villa Bissinger* (Institut International des vins de Champagne, 2010), 152.

²³ Claudine Wolikow, “La délimitation de la Champagne“ in *Les Cahiers de la Villa Bissinger* (Institut International des vins de Champagne, 2010), 155.

²⁴ Claudine Wolikow, “La délimitation de la Champagne“ in *Les Cahiers de la Villa Bissinger* (Institut International des vins de Champagne, 2010), 158.

Bibliographic review on the events erupted in 1911 in Champagne

According to Claudine Wolikow, the history of the uprisings in 1911 is intimately linked with the history of the delimitation of the Champagne wine region. Indeed, the delimitation process exploded social and economic factors in both of the departments of the Marne and the Aube. Since 1930, the academic field and in particular social sciences studied this specific event under different perspectives. Historians with local and national approaches studied the social origins and the role played by winegrowers and political parties in the events.

Claudine Wolikow is a historian from the department of the Aube and a member of the UNESCO Chair “Culture and Traditions of Wines” at the University of Burgundy. Her research is devoted to the history of the implementation of the French certification called *appellation d’origine contrôlée*. The certification is a legal regulation of the production and commercialization of specific products such as wine and cheese. It protects the name of the products corresponding to specific geographical areas. She is studying this question in relation to the Champagne wine region between 1903-1927. Her analysis is based on parliamentary debates, decrees, laws and other legal documents. Wolikow believes that the delimitation process was launched locally as part of the national agenda that had begun in the early nineteenth century, and in particular with the adoption of the Chaptal act in 1824. She explains by several arguments the different reasons of the events in the article untitled “La delimitation de la Champagne viticole” (The delimitation of the Champagne wine region) published in 2010 in the revue of the International Institute of wines of Champagne. As for that matter, she argues, based on the archive of the local and national press, that the events of 1911 were “revolts” which transformed into “riots”²⁵. While the events in the Marne were qualified in the press as riots and

²⁵ Claudine Wolikow, “La délimitation de la Champagne” in *Les Cahiers de la Villa Bissinger* (Institut International des vins de Champagne, 2010), 147.

jacquerie at the national level, in the Aube, the events were described as pacific manifestations and symbolic violence. With regard to the explanation offered for the reasons of the events, Wolikow begins by stressing that the revolt was a reaction to the fraud that drove prices downward. Besides the fraud, the low quantity of the harvest between 1907–1910 caused mainly by the phylloxera and the bad meteorological conditions gave rise to existential uncertainty among the winegrowers. In the second place, she argues that the delimitation process played an important role in the uprising as it added to the growing tensions. Finally, she evokes that it is important to note that an opposition existed, presented further, between the two departments at the beginning of the 20th century caused by two political majorities that governed the two departmental assemblies.²⁶

Indeed, Wolikow further argues that in addition to the economic difficulties, the political context varied in each department of the Marne and of the Aube. She explains that behaviours in the department of the Marne were characterized of two major political currents: corporate solidarism and Christian socialism. On the one hand, solidarism was embodied locally by the figure of Léon Bourgeois who was supported by the majority of elected representatives and a large number of trade union leaders. On the other hand, Christian socialism was widespread among some of the directors of the champagne trade houses (for example Veuve Clicquot). Although ideologically the two branches are different, they converge in the sense that both reject the idea of class struggle and seek to promote the reconciliation of social interests. In the Aube, “guesdisme” named after the leader Jules Guesde and the founder of the French Workers' Party is reputed.²⁷ However, the figure of the events of 1911 was Gaston Cheq. He was a

²⁶ Claudine Wolikow, “La délimitation de la Champagne“ in *Les Cahiers de la Villa Bissinger* (Institut International des vins de Champagne, 2010), 151.

²⁷ Claudine Wolikow, “La délimitation de la Champagne“ in *Les Cahiers de la Villa Bissinger* (Institut International des vins de Champagne, 2010), 151.

socialist and the founder of the Federation of winegrowers of the Aube. He underlined the importance of “staying in union” to confront the decision of the Senate on the delimitation area.²⁸

Compared to Wolikow, Jacques Girault, a historian at the Paris-Sorbonne University and specialized in the labour movements is more critical about the role of the socialists in the events of 1911 in the Aube. Girault published an article entitled “*Le rôle du socialisme dans la révolte des vigneron de l’Aube*” (The role of socialism in the revolt of the Aube winegrowers) in 1969 in a revue entitled “*Le Mouvement social*” (The social movement). Girault is interested in the question of the degree by which the socialists influenced the events which he qualifies as a matter of fact as “movements,” “protests” and “revolts.” His article discusses the relationship between the share of the vote of socialists in the result of the local elections in wine growing and non-wine growing villages in the Aube. He analyses the percentage of winegrowers who voted for socialist elected representatives (from the French Section of the Workers’ International party), meanwhile he attempt to explicate that it is hardly possible to carry out a generalization on winegrowing villages that are more socialist than others.²⁹ Thus, in the final analysis, Girault argues that the events of 1911 were not inspired by socialist ideas. Yet, he specifies that it was actually a struggle of small property owners. Indeed, winegrowers rarely owned more than two hectares of vine that were also, in many cases, dispersed in the region.³⁰ Girault’s point is that socialists did not manage to lead the protest. He notes that the only socialist who has played a leading role as a reformer in the figure of Gaston Cheq. According to Girault, the socialists have allowed themselves to be dragged along by the radicals for solutions by proposing reforms.³¹

²⁸ Claudine Wolikow, “La délimitation de la Champagne” in *Les Cahiers de la Villa Bissinger* (Institut International des vins de Champagne, 2010), 152.

²⁹ Jacques Girault, “Le rôle du socialisme dans la révolte des vigneron de l’Aube”, *Le Mouvement social* 67 (1969): 90.

³⁰ Claire Desbois-Thibault, “La Champagne face à son histoire” *La Champagne viticole*, hors-série (2011):13.

³¹ Jacques Girault, “Le rôle du socialisme dans la révolte des vigneron de l’Aube”, *Le Mouvement social* 67 (1969): 109.

He adds that social transformations appeared in the argument of the demonstrators in a general way even if, for some, these events remain "socialist in the manner of the great Jaures."³²

In the same review, Jacqueline Saillet analyses the events in the Marne in an article titled "*Les mouvements vignerons de Champagne*" (The movements of the Champagne winegrowers). Her analysis invokes the role of the socialists, the Federation of the unions of the Marne, the anarchists and the trade houses in the events. In an absorbing introductory chapter, the author describes first the role of that Federation which was, according to her, mainly in contact with the deputies. Second, she explains, that as for the trade houses, the events turned out to be a commercial tool in their publicities to communicate the renewal of the champagne region. Three, as for the designation of the events of 1911, Saillet argues for the use of the term "social riots," as they expressed primarily a discontent of wine growers, viticultural laborers and craftsmen, with regard to unpredictable economic and social situation. Four, she concludes, as Girault, that the demonstrations were not inspired by Socialism, and its origins were not related to the vote of the Senate on the delimitation of the wine region, but rather to poverty.

The Society of the amateurs of Champagne folklore and arts, created in 1958 which pooled local amateur historians, published three special issues in their revue entitled "*Folklore de Champagne*" about the uprisings in the Aube and in the Marne. The first was published in 1979, written by Françoise Weinling. This issue of the revue addressed the events in the Aube in 1911, in particular in Bar-sur-Aube and Bar-sur-Seine. Weinling qualifies the events as "movements" and as "revolts." She describes the different striking methods used during the manifestations, such as the red flag, or the international anthem. Although she believes that these two main symbols of the socialism were not linked to political ideas but were borrowed to symbolize the

³² Jacques Girault, "Le rôle du socialisme dans la révolte des vignerons de l'Aube", *Le Mouvement social* 67 (1969): 109.

discontentment of the winegrowers and to express their opposition to the government concerning their decision on the delimitation area. She argues that the objective of the manifestations was not to change the social system, even if the question on social class appeared, but to be part of the Champagne region and thus to assure livelihoods from wine growing. Weinling points out that the idea to “stay in unity” spread by Gaston Cheq was possible because of the misery.³³

Image 2: “Bread first. Politics after.” A call to the Union of the Central Committee of Barsur-Aube ends with these terms.³⁴

The second review was published in 1981 on the events in the Marne between 1894 and 1911. The third one was published one year later and it analyzed the revolt in the Marne of the year of 1911, from January to April. The author of the two reviews was Gérard Munier, a local amateur historian. He defined the events as a “popular revolt,” and described two “revolutions”³⁵ in Champagne. The first one took place in 1894 and the second one in 1911. He

³³ Weinling Françoise, “La révolte dans le Barséquanaise, 1991. Une grande année dans le vignoble aubois“, *Folklore de Champagne* 67, (1979): 21.

³⁴ Weinling Françoise, “La révolte dans le Barséquanaise, 1991. Une grande année dans le vignoble aubois“, *Folklore de Champagne* 67, (1979): 23.

³⁵ Munier Gérard. “Les révoltes en Marne“, *Folklore de Champagne* 75, (1981):16.

argues that the discontentment of the winegrowers had already begun with the establishment of the Departmental Defence Union, created in 1891 in order to implement measures against the phylloxera. The Union was financed by the Ministry of Agriculture, the municipalities of Reims and Epernay and the Chamber of Commerce of Reims. The articles of the Union prescribed 58 members and 25 elected representatives with a director of the Union. An official list was represented by mainly trade houses, on the head M. Verrier, and an opposition list was also represented by wine growers with René Lamarre.³⁶

Despite the elected opposition list, due to the subsidies granted, the representatives of some of the trade houses (de Cazenave, Mercier, Bollinger, Chandon etc.) also became members of the Union. By then, wine growers refused to cooperate. They rejected the measures taken by the Union to treat phylloxera, because they appeared to them as imposed from above. When vineyard inspectors appeared on their property, winegrowers drove them away. René Lamarre founded a local journal called “*La Révolution Champenoise*” (The Champagne Revolution) in 1891, and initiated a protest movement in June 1892. He accused the trade houses of being the source of the misery of the wine growers: “Phylloxera isn’t the only parasite in our vineyards.”³⁷ The protesters demanded the abolishment of taxes for 1892, and that they be value-added (and not be defined based on the land value of the wine). However, the Union ceased its activity in 1896.

Munier considers that the revolt which took place in April 1911 was the second one. He explores the events from April to June 1911 with rich photo documentation. He argues that the events had a double aspect which created an “air of revolution.”³⁸ According to Munier, political

³⁶ Munier Gérard. “Les révoltes en Marne“, *Folklore de Champagne* 75, (1981): 17.

³⁷ Munier Gérard, “La révolte marnaise, 1911“, *Folklore de Champagne* 78, (1982): 35

³⁸ Munier Gérard, “La révolte marnaise, 1911“, *Folklore de Champagne* 78, (1982): 78.

parties did not participate in the revolt, but political ideas played a large role in it, such as reforming society, fighting misery, injustice and exploitation by putting the emphasis on trade unions and cooperatives.³⁹ He concludes that if socialists did not play an important role in the demonstrations, they nevertheless influenced the “revolution of social relations through new economic relations,” for instance by the creation of the unions and cooperatives.⁴⁰ This argument is based on evidence which shows that the objective of many winegrowers was not to change the government or the political regime, but to take action in order to bring in new regulations which could repress the fraud.⁴¹

Paul Piard, in his thesis entitled “*Des syndicats vers la corporation: L’organisation de la Champagne viticole*” (From unions to the corporation: The organization of the Champagne wine region), defended in 1937 at the Faculty of Law of Paris analyzed the legal regulations and administrative measures which have governed the production and the sales of champagne wines in the beginning of the 20th century.⁴² He studies a period of thirty years. He relates the events of 1911 to the delimitation process and the fraud. For Piard, the events can be considered as riots, rebellions, agitations and protestations. He analyzes the role and the interests of different organizations taking part in the wine commerce on a local level. According to him, it was the erroneous ideology of liberal economy, developed by certain economic theorists, that allowed the emergence of fraud.⁴³ The unions marked the first step towards the constitution of a corporation of the champagne wine producers. As a result, the components of this corporation were based on three levels: on the basis are the traders' and winegrowers' unions; above them,

³⁹ Munier Gérard. “Les révoltes en Marne“, *Folklore de Champagne* 75, (1981): 15.

⁴⁰ Munier Gérard, “La révolte marnaise“, 1911, *Folklore de Champagne* 78, (1982): 54.

⁴¹ Munier Gérard, “La révolte marnaise“, 1911, *Folklore de Champagne* 78, (1982): 41.

⁴² Paul Piard, “*Des syndicats vers la corporation: L’organisation de la Champagne viticole*“, (Université de Paris – Faculté de droit, 1937), 12.

⁴³ Paul Piard, “*Des syndicats vers la corporation: L’organisation de la Champagne viticole*“, (Université de Paris – Faculté de droit, 1937), 290.

there is a special commission for champagne wines; and a national committee is situated on the top for controlled designations of origin. Piard concludes that even if individual interests motivated the local actors until the beginning of the 20th century, finally a common organization system had been set up representing the collective interests of wine growers and trade houses.

Hereafter, we can conclude that the events of 1911 were widely studied by historians in different formats: scientific and critical articles, thesis, local reviews. Furthermore, we can mention entire books which were dedicated to the subject, for example, one published in 2011 by Dominique Fradet entitled “*1911 en Champagne, Chronique d’une révolution*” (1911 in Champagne, Chronicle of a revolution) which adopts the tone of a novel as it narrates the events from October 1910 to November 1911 in the Aube and the Marne. Another two books, marking the centenary of the events, were published as well. One, entitled “*Les révoltes du champagne*” (Champagne revolts), written by Yann Harlaut and Fabrice Perron and the second entitled “*Champagne! Histoire inattendue*” (*Champagne! Unexpected history!*) by Claudine Wolikow and Serge Wolikow. The authors of the first book are historians at the Reims Champagne-Ardenne University. Their book provides a narrative of the uprisings, from the arrival of the phylloxera, through the manifestations against the fraud and the delimitation process. Regarding its format, the book is close to an album with rich photo archive illustrations. The second book of Wolikow’s presents a global history of the Champagne wine region from the start of the production of white sparkling wine dating back to the XVII century until nowadays. The various interpretations presented above show the different formats and styles adopted to narrate the events of 1911 in Champagne. Beyond the characteristics concerning the style and format of the publications, we can also observe that different terms are used to qualify the events, such as riot, revolt, revolution or crisis. The textual approach draws attention to the lack of the definition of these terms, which appears rather to express an upheaval and unforeseen

change or fight. Thus, we can argue that the notion of revolution or revolt is a flexible idea that can be adapted to a wide variety of contexts. It supposes a constantly changing definition of the concept of revolution since the seventeenth and the twentieth centuries.⁴⁴ The examination of the different research (legislative, political, sociological, economic) carried out by historians allows to compare the various interpretations of the events. The research proposes a broader and more nuanced understanding of the society of viticulture in the end of the nineteenth and the beginning of the twentieth century in France and in particular in Champagne. If authors like Claudine Wolikow or Desbois-Thibault closely connected the unfolding events to the delimitation process, others, like Girault or Saillet highlighted the fact that the main factor of the eruption of the events was the misery of the winegrowers. Based on the analysis of Piard and Meunier, the events contributed to the development of numerous trade unions.

Nevertheless, the subject of the delimitation process was present in all of the analysis carried out by the authors. In the Aube, the first manifestations appeared after the decision of the Senate in 1908 excluding the department from the Champagne production area. In the Marne, the fraud and the economic uncertainty followed by the phylloxera provoked the first manifestations. The demonstrations raised the question of poverty in both of the regions. The initiation of the delimitation process by trade houses in the Marne appeared as a tool to regulate the wine market and to propose a legal economic frame for the production of sparkling white wine. The impact of the events overpassed the delimitation issue on the local level, and it became a subject on a national level. In 1935, the National Institute of the Designation of Origin has been created with the *appellation d'origine contrôlée* certification. The harsh tensions between trade houses and winegrowers increased the demand to establish a strict organization in the wine market. This

⁴⁴ Rachel Hammersley, "Introduction", *Revolutionary moments, Reading revolutionary texts*, (Bloomsbury Academic, (2015).

organization was created in 1941: Interprofessional Comity of the Champagne, representing the interests of winegrowers and trade houses. This inter-professional organization in Champagne became a model and has subsequently been adopted in other wine regions, such as Burgundy, Bordeaux, Languedoc etc.

Conclusion

This article attempted to present the events which took place in 1911 in two different administrative areas: the departments of the Marne and the Aube, situated in the Champagne wine region. In the first part of the article, we described the social and economic context of the Champagne region from the end of the nineteenth century until the beginning of the 20th century. In the second part, we presented the legal history of the delimitation process of the wine region which was connected by some historians as one of the main reasons of the events, beyond the consequences of the phylloxera and the prevailing misery of social conditions. We also reconstructed the demonstrations that responded to the delimitation process. Finally, in the third part, we proposed an analysis of how historians and amateur ones interpreted the events of 1911. The range of texts examined is deliberately broad which gives particular attention to the sequence of events. It also shows that in the majority, local historians (from the Aube and the Marne) studied the triggering factors and circumstances of the events, by calling it a revolution, revolt or riot inspired by headlined of local journals to show mainly the upheaval of the events.

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